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Synthesis and Characterisation of Mixed Tri-heteropoly Potassium 5-Molybdo-niobotellurate(VI)

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SCANTY references are found in chemical literature¹⁻³ for mixed heteropoly niobates and tantalates. A few heteropoly-niobotungstates $[\text{Nb}_6\text{W}_{6-x}\text{O}_{19}]^{(2+x)-}$ ($x=1-4$) has been isolated from aqueous solution⁴. We have investigated the replacement of molybdenum by niobium in the well characterised⁵ 6-heteropoly-anion $[\text{TeMo}_6\text{O}_{24}]^{6-}$, and the results are reported here.

Experimental

Potassium 5-molybdoniobotellurate: Molybdic acid (2.55 g) dissolved in water (250 ml) and telluric acid (0.5 g) dissolved in water (50 ml) were mixed with constant stirring, and to the mixture glacial acetic acid was added to maintain pH 3.6. To it, freshly prepared⁶ potassium orthohexaniobate (0.59 g) dissolved in water (50 ml) was added with constant stirring keeping the pH constant. The stoichiometric proportion of Mo, Nb and Te in the reaction mixture was 5 : 1 : 1. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h in CO_2 -free atmosphere. The solution was then concentrated to yield light yellow niddle shaped transparent crystals (Found: Mo, 27.55; Nb, 5.2; Te, 7.35; K, 15.6; H, 2.4; O, 41.9. $\text{K}_7[\text{TeNbMo}_5\text{O}_{24}]\cdot 19\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd. for: Mo, 28.23; Nb, 5.47; Te, 7.50; K, 16.0; H, 2.23; O, 40.57%); ν_{max} 3 460, 3 290, 1 625, 950, 890, 840, 690, 620, 580, 550, 450 and 325 cm^{-1} .

Molybdenum⁷ and niobium⁸ were estimated gravimetrically, and the values were checked up by colorimetric determinations⁹. Tellurium was also estimated gravimetrically¹⁰. Potassium in the compound was estimated by perchloric method.

Results and Discussion

The medium and sharp ir peaks of $\text{K}_7(\text{TeNbMo}_5\text{O}_{24})\cdot 19\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 950, 890, 840 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Mo-O-Mo}}$ bridging^{3,11}. The sharp peaks at 690 and 325 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu_{\text{Te-O}}$ stretching in octahedral coordination¹¹⁻¹³. The

sharp bands at 620 and 450 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu_{\text{Nb-O}}$ linkage¹⁴. The broad bands for ν_{OH} of lattice water was observed at 3 460–3 290, δ_{HOH} around 1 625 and π_{OH} mode in 580–550 cm^{-1} range^{11,15}.

For stepwise decomposition of water molecules, the heating of the compound at fixed temperatures ranging from 50 to 300° with an increase of 50° in each turn, was performed in a muffle furnace. The number of water molecules lost at the successive temperatures were 6, 4, 3, 3 and 2. The complete decomposition of the compound at 300° was observed by eliminating the remaining single water molecule. For further corroboration, DTA and TGA analyses¹⁶ of the compound were performed under nitrogen at a heating rate of 5° min^{-1} . The endothermic peaks between 50 to 250° correspond to dehydration of the compound. The complete degradation of the heteropoly cage at 300° was confirmed by exothermic peaks at 300 ± 10° at which chemical analysis of the sample indicated the existence of mixed oxides of the metal. At this stage insolubility of the heated sample in water also confirmed the complete decomposition of the heteropoly salt.

X-Ray crystal diffraction analysis of the compound was recorded using rotation and Weissenberg photographs using single isolated crystal. The crystal data found were $a=11.62$, $b=14.25$, $c=10.22$ Å $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$; cubic system volume per unit cell $v=1692.278$ Å³; number of unit cell contained $z=2$; density $d=3.36$ cm^{-3} ; molecular weight $M=1712$ (calcd. 1699).

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